

**Conflict, memory and positioning. Studying the dialogical and multivoiced
dimension of the Basque conflict.**

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Abstract

This paper aims to bring the dialogical and multivoiced dimension of conflicts to the fore when studying how people remember a particular event in the past. Drawing from different case studies, it analyses how subjects, identified with different political actors in the Basque conflict, adopt their respective positioning and interpretation of the conflict, and how, in light of same, they reconstruct the failed peace process that took place in 2006 between the terrorist group ETA and the Spanish Government. Results show that the positioning adopted by participants gives rise to a certain form of interpreting the conflict which, in turn, affects how the peace process is remembered. This occurs within a particular argumentative context in which each version constitutes an implicit response to a competing interpretation of the peacemaking process. However, apart from this dialogical relationship between versions, we can also find an internal dialogicality within certain accounts of the peace process, whereby a dialogue between voices linked to different positions is established. The paper concludes with a discussion on the role of history teaching in promoting a more critical, reflexive and pluralistic way of dealing with memory, and hence with conflicts.

Keywords: dialogicality; multivoicedness; positioning; narrative; memory

Introduction

The 22nd of March 2006 was a day that inspired hope for the Basque conflict in Spain¹. That morning, the armed group ETA (acronym for *Euzkadi ta Azcatasuna* or *Basque Country and Freedom* in English) announced a “permanent ceasefire”. However, the hope generated by that statement was not devoid of controversy, something which reared its head from the outset on account of the different ways in which the main figures involved in the conflict read into both the announcement *per se* and the new era which that announcement seemed to herald. In its statement, ETA justified the commencement of the ceasefire by its desire to promote a democratic process in the Basque Country whereby that region’s right to self-determination would be recognized. The Spanish Government (headed at that time by the Socialist President José Luís Rodríguez Zapatero) considered the ceasefire as an opportunity to commence a peace process with ETA and its political arm (the party known as *Batasuna*), which would enable a peaceful solution to be found to a conflict spanning almost four decades. The People’s Party (the main centre-right party and then Opposition) classed the ceasefire as a “truce-trap” and questioned the Government’s authority to negotiate with the armed group. It furthermore indicated that ETA’s decision had come about in response to a series of prior contacts held between the terrorist group and the Government itself.

¹ The Basque Country is a region situated in the northern part of Spain endowed with specific cultural characteristics (e.g., the Basque language or *Euskara*) and a high level of political autonomy. Due to the strong sense of identity of this region, a significant number of people in the Basque Country do not feel part of the Spanish nation and would like this region to be an independent country. This scenario is strongly marked by the presence of the Basque terrorist group ETA. Since its first armed action in 1969 (at the end of Franco’s dictatorship), this group has caused nearly 900 casualties, including politicians, civilians and military men. However, after fifty years of violence, along with some failed peace processes (including that of 2006), ETA has been losing strength in terms of both its operational capacity and social support. In October 2011, ETA announced the definitive cessation of its armed activity. The conflict has still not been definitively resolved since the Spanish government is waiting for ETA to relinquish its arms.

On the 30th of December, nine months after the ceasefire, ETA planted a bomb in a car park at Madrid airport, which went off causing two deaths. That attack was the culmination of nine months of heightened tension during which the main political actors devised various accounts in order to legitimize their own form of acting and positioning themselves in respect of a process understood as the “democratic process”, “peace process” or “trick process”, depending on the version. Thus, following the attack, different ways of understanding that process were consolidated by means of various accounts that seemed to contradict and oppose one another. In fact, the presence of those different versions clearly reflected the gaping political and social division that continues to exist in Spain in respect of the Basque conflict. In that regard, those accounts also acted as tools by which people could interpret, recall and draw conclusions from the ceasefire depending on the extent to which they identified with the main figures involved.

In this paper, we will tackle this last point by examining, through different case studies, the way in which a number of subjects, identified with certain positions on the Basque conflict, reconstruct the controversial truce period through different narratives. In that sense, we seek to emphasise the socio-cultural dimension of remembering. So, far from conceiving remembering as an independent faculty that operates in a vacuum in search of an accurate reproduction of the past, we understand it, in line with Bartlett’s (1932) reasoning, as a socio-culturally situated activity aimed at reconstructing and giving meaning to the past in order to meet different demands and purposes (see also Brescó & Wagoner, in press). Here, meaning-making is therefore crucial, as is the mediational role of narratives through which individuals and groups interpret and link the events of the past by means of a plot and a certain theme. Thus, in line with a Cultural

Psychology perspective (Cole, 1996), we consider narratives as meaning-making tools provided by a particular socio-cultural setting that are used as a resource in remembering (Wertsch, 2002). In the case in hand, that setting is marked by a nationalist conflict in which various political actors have different ways of understanding the ceasefire episode in accordance with their respective positioning on the Basque problem. In that regard, the accounts of the ceasefire produced by those participating in our study will be analysed in light of the position of the main figures involved in that episode. The extent to which the participants make those figures' interpretation of the truce period their own will be observed.

Theoretical Background

Dialogicality and Positioning in Nationalist Conflicts

Conflict and dialogicality usually go hand in hand, in that every conflict calls for at least two possible forms of understanding and adopting a position in the face of a problem, with the rationale behind each positioning lying in the existence of an opposite positioning which it attempts to refute and counter. This results in a dialogical relationship between the different positions, giving rise to what Wertsch (2002) calls a *hidden dialogism*, whereby each position on the conflict constitutes an implicit response to a competing interpretation. This dialogical relationship therefore takes place within an *argumentative context* (Billig, 1987) characterized by the presence of different voices and storylines which ultimately compete to impose their own form of defining or thematizing the conflict according to the different claims of each party concerned (e.g., by indicating what the conflict is about, when it was initiated and by whom, and what must be done in order to restore the status quo and rule of law). Thus, in defining the

very nature of the conflict, such storylines allocate blame or legitimacy among the warring factions involved by appealing to certain norms or principles.

This applies to nationalist-based conflicts insofar as the claims of the parties typically rely on a common principle, inherent to any kind of nationalism, according to which the political and the national unit must be congruent, or in other words, every nation should be politically sovereign and consequently should have their own state (Gellner, 1983). In fact, the present worldwide assumption of the nationalist outlook has rendered this principle natural and commonsensical. However, problems begin to arise when it comes to fleshing out this abstract principle and, more specifically, when defining the very idea of the nation and delimiting its corresponding territory. This happens in contexts such as the Basque conflict in which a group perceives itself as a nation and, consequently, does not feel legitimately represented by the overarching structure of the state. As Billig (2001) points out, “when groups declare themselves to be national groups, they are making particular political statements, evoking an ideological history of entitlements and rights” (p. 219). Such a situation results in varying degrees of political unrest in which every group seeks to historically define the conflict and thus justify the attribution of certain political or territorial rights to itself.

Positioning theory addresses “the study of the way rights and duties are taken up and laid down, ascribed and appropriated, refused and defended in the fine grain of the encounters of daily lives” (Harré & Moghaddam, 2011, p.132). This framework has also been applied to situations and conflicts with a greater timescale (see Moghaddam & Kavulich, 2008). In these cases, positioning refers to the set of rights and duties that different political actors, such as groups or states, discursively attribute both to

themselves and to other actors according to the way in which they define the very nature of the conflict. In the case of nationalist conflicts—such as the Basque conflict—we typically find two general positionings corresponding to different ways of applying the abovementioned nation-state unit principle. Thus, defining the conflict as one derived from an attempt to subvert the existing national state unit may lead to a positioning that claims the right to preserve the constitutional order and the duty to defend it against any separatist attack. Conversely, defining the conflict as one caused by the oppression of a state against the free will of a national community may result in a positioning that claims that it is the duty of that state to recognize the right of such community to self-determination, a community which, in turn, might undertake the duty to fight for such a right, even by resorting to force.

Dialogicality and Positioning within the self

Positionings are instantiated through discourse. As Harré (2005) points out, “duties and rights exist in the discursive domain” (p. 237). In nationalist conflicts, the duties and rights claimed by each group are usually justified according to different ways of understanding the conflict which, in turn, are based on certain discourses on the past, a past which is normally construed in national terms serving the identity designs of each group concerned. Memory and identity are therefore two sides of the same coin. On the one hand, it is well known that the transmission of historical narratives constitutes a key factor in the creation of a shared sense of the past and consequently for the generation of an *imagined community* (Anderson, 1983) based on a collective feeling of belonging. On the other hand, however, memory and identity can contribute towards keeping conflicts ignited, insofar as each group bases its positioning and claims on certain forms of recounting the past. In both cases, narratives constitute indispensable tools enabling

individuals to identify themselves with their groups, as well as with their claims and forms of interpreting conflicts. In this way, remembering also occurs within an argumentative context characterized by the presence of different and contrasting narratives which, in conveying a way of defining or thematizing the conflict, provide a criterion by which people select, interpret, appraise, and even infer facts in a way that fits a predetermined storyline.

However, this mediational role of narratives does not imply that people do not have their own voice and that they merely repeat the discourses of their group in a passive manner. As Wertsch (forthcoming) points out, “narrative tools do not mechanistically determine human discourse and thinking. Instead, the very notion of a tool implies an active user and suggests an element of variability and freedom” (p. 5). This leads us to the question of agency when studying how people reconstruct the past, and particularly, the history of conflicts. Echoing the Bakhtinian question one might ask: *Who is doing the talking? To whom does the voice belong?* According to *dialogical self theory* (Hermans, 2001), both the self and culture are conceived as a multiplicity of positionings and voices among which dialogical relationships can be established. Thus, the varying amount of positionings and voices that characterize societies also operates within the dialogical self, which is conceived as a *society of mind* insofar as “like a society, the self is involved in oppositions, agreements, disagreements, contradictions, negotiations and integrations” (Hermans, 2002, p.148).

However, the dialogical dimension of the self may vary depending on the capability of bringing the argumentative context of social issues into self-talk or, in other words, to convert *heterodialogue* between voices and positionings in society into *autodialogue*

within the self (Valsiner, 2002)². Here, agency has not vanished amidst the multiplicity of social voices. In fact, internal dialogue is a necessary element for individuals to contrast different positionings and go beyond them, thus opening the door to the construction of new and more personal ones. We can therefore find different degrees of agency and authorship. On the one hand, the multivoicedness of the dialogical self constitutes the basis for the personalizing transformation of social discourses (Lawrence & Valsiner, 2003). On the other hand, the monologization of the dialogical self implies the dominance of one voice through which the person would be talked, or ventriloquized (Bakhtin, 1981), by certain social actors, thus limiting the possibility of adopting different and more personal positions. As Hermans and Kempen (1993) point out, “dominance, as an intrinsic feature of dialogue, not only organizes but restricts the multiplicity of possible positions in the process of socialization” (p. 73).

The case study: Remembering the peace process of 2006 in the Basque Country

The study presented below³ seeks to bring the dialogical and multivoiced dimension of the Basque conflict to the fore when studying how people remember the truce period described above. In particular, it analyses how subjects, identified to varying extents with different political actors, adopt their respective positioning and interpretation of the conflict, and how, in light of same, they reconstruct the truce period with the aid of a set of journalistic documents relating to that event. Narrative mediation is therefore crucial here for it is expected that participants will make sense of the abovementioned documents by means of the storylines provided by the different political actors involved in the episode. However, it is also expected that different uses of these narratives will be

² This viewpoint is in line with the sociogenetic theories in Psychology (Vygotsky, 1987) which “emphasize the social beginnings of human ideas and meanings and their movement from the inter-psychological world to the intra-psychological world and back again” (Lawrence & Valsiner, 2003, p. 724).

³ This study is an extension of previous studies (see Brescó, 2009; Brescó & Wagoner, forthcoming).

found according to the degree of identification with the main political actors, ranging from a monological reproduction of the group's version to a more personalized and dialogical account in which different voices can be heard.

Subjects

Sixteen undergraduate students participated in this study (eight from the Autonomous University of Madrid and eight from the University of the Basque Country), of which four have been included in this paper: two from the Basque Country and two from Madrid. In order to make the multivoiced dimension of the conflict more visible, we have selected three more monological accounts from participants clearly identified with the three main actors involved in the peace process⁴ and one subject with a more personalized and dialogical account of that episode.

Materials and Procedure

The data collection process involved a visit by the first author to both the Autonomous University of Madrid and the University of the Basque Country. The participation involved the following three tasks:

1) Thematization of the Basque conflict: participants were first asked to give a brief definition of the Basque conflict (in order to provide a baseline from which they had already thematized the Basque conflict) followed by its corresponding resolution.

2) Presentation of news sources for developing an account of the peace process: on completion of the previous task, each participant was given three sheets of paper

⁴ These actors are: 1) the Spanish Government; 2) ETA and its political arm Batasuna; and 3) the right-wing People's Party, the main party of the Opposition at that time.

containing 23 short documents on the 2006 peacemaking process extracted from various Spanish newspapers⁵. Those documents, arranged chronologically, were composed of five pictures, ten broadsheet headings and eight brief excerpts of statements delivered by the main political actors involved in the process.

3) Writing a story about the peace process: participants were then asked to look at the material that had been handed out and write a short account of the peacemaking process. It was emphasized that there were neither good nor bad stories, and that we were primarily interested in collecting their own version of the episode. Subjects were allowed to use and interpret the sources however they wished, for example, only using documents which already supported their views, omitting those which they found irrelevant or which conflicted with their views, and adding whatever extra information they considered appropriate.

Results

*Participant 1: Green*⁶ – Our first subject is an 18-year-old male who studies psychology at the University of the Basque Country and who identifies with Batasuna's positioning. The following is Green's original thematization of the Basque conflict and a possible resolution prior to the presentation of the news sources:

Thematization of the Basque conflict: *"It is a conflict between an oppressed nation and two oppressor states (Spain and France) which refuse to recognize the right all*

⁵ All political views were balanced across sources. The selected sources were: "El Mundo" and "ABC" (center-right newspapers, close to the People's Party), "El País" (center-left newspaper, close to the Socialist Party), "Gara" (newspaper close to Batasuna, ETA's political arm), and "La Vanguardia" (a Catalan center-right newspaper).

⁶ In order to protect the anonymity of participants, we will provide them all with code names.

democratic states have: the right to self-determination. This situation has led to an armed conflict.”

Conflict resolution: *“Negotiations should involve all political options. The aforementioned states should give Basque citizens the right to decide their own future. Then ETA would declare another truce. Regardless, whenever ETA has declared a truce, the Spanish state has continued to repress, detain and ban Basque political parties.”*

Here, it can be observed that upon identifying himself with Batasuna’s positioning, this participant has interpreted the conflict in light of the alleged oppression of the Basque people by the Spanish and French states. Thus, in accordance with this positioning and the ensuing resolution of the conflict, we can identify the following attribution of rights and duties: first of all, there is the right of the Basque nation to be heard and to be able to decide its own future. In parallel, the Spanish state has the duty to listen to the Basque people and to recognize their right to self-determination. Lastly, where those terms are not met, ETA has the right to take up arms.

Green’s account of the peacemaking process is as follows:

“ETA declares a truce and ceases all its actions. The Government says that it is willing to meet with ETA. Batasuna expresses its willingness to negotiate the future of the Basque Country. The Spanish state keeps imprisoning, torturing and oppressing the Basque People, especially Batasuna and its supporters. Given the course of events and the Government’s inability to move forward, ETA decides to send out a warning to the

Government by planting a bomb at Madrid airport. The Government doesn't react and the truce comes to an end. Then, ETA returns to its armed struggle."

As demonstrated by this version of events, despite ETA's good intentions, the Spanish Government failed in its democratic duty by not listening to the Basque people, thereby causing ETA to exercise its right to resume the armed struggle. It is also worth noting that in order to support his version of events, this participant omitted all documents (included among the material handed out to the subjects) referring to ETA's violent activities during the ceasefire, and instead used the news article from *Gara* which spoke of arrests and torture vis-à-vis Batasuna and its supporters. Here, it is the Government that is responsible for the truce's failure by not responding to ETA's warning in the form of a bomb attack. This is a peculiar way of constructing the peacemaking process; one in which violence is seen as a form of dialogue.

Participant 2: Red – The second subject, "Red", is a 19-year-old male who studies psychology in Madrid. He sympathizes with the Socialist Party and with its positioning on the Basque issue, at that time more inclined to negotiate a way out of the conflict. Red's view on both the conflict and a possible resolution is as follows:

Thematization of the Basque conflict: *"It started as a conflict centred on the Basque collective identity and rights. However, nowadays it is an armed conflict centred on political, economic and social interests."*

Conflict resolution: *“Arms must give way to words. More dialogue and consensus among all the political parties (including both Batasuna and the People’s Party) is required. The Basque language and identity must be preserved”*.

As can be noted, Red thematizes the conflict as one that arises out of different economic and political interests where arms prevail over words, though he also recognizes that it stems from identity. From this positioning we can infer that the Government has both the duty and the right to seek dialogue and consensus. It is also its duty to preserve the Basque cultural identity. By the same token, the Basque nation has the right to both defend its culture and have it preserved by the Spanish Government. In turn, it is ETA’s duty to exchange arms for words. Thus, contrary to Green’s thematization of the issue, the armed struggle is not regarded as forming part of the solution but as one of its main problems and also the major impediment to dialogue. It thus follows that both Batasuna and the People’s Party have a duty to support dialogue and consensus.

Based on this way of understanding the conflict, Red produced the following account of the truce period:

“ETA announces a ceasefire followed by a dialogue-based peace plan which is supported by all political parties except the right (People’s Party). From the very beginning there is constant opposition from the right, which jeopardized the process. In fact, the right organized several demonstrations with the sole aim of making the peace process fail. They tainted the Socialist Party with conspiracy theories and accused Zapatero of yielding to ETA’s claims despite the fact that during that time the Government arrested more individuals than any previous administration. In turn, ETA

kept using violent means. Given the fact that an agreement could not be reached (where you have to first lose in order to win), ETA broke the ceasefire, thus ruining any chance of maintaining the dialogue. However, despite the failure, it was worth a try, wasn't it?"

As can be observed from Red's account, the truce's failure is attributed to both the People's Party and ETA. As regards the People's Party, this participant highlights the conspiracy theories put forward by the right and the accusations of surrender made against the Government, which Red contrasts with the large number of arrests made during the peacemaking process. Whilst in this case the reference to the arrests serves to offset the accusations levied against the Government for not complying with its duty to fight against ETA, the previous subject referred to the arrests in order to illustrate the Government's failure to comply with its duty to respect the ceasefire. As for ETA's role, Red's version, unlike Green's, makes reference to the violent activities carried out by ETA, which were a key factor in the breakdown of the truce.

Participant 3: Blue – The third subject is an 18-year-old female who studies psychology in Madrid and sympathizes with the right-wing People's Party. She defined the conflict and its possible resolution in the following terms:

Thematization of the Basque conflict: *"There is a group of people from that region who don't feel Spanish so they use violence."*

Conflict resolution: *"Increase police involvement, toughen the laws and eliminate the anti-Spanish feeling instilled into pupils in their schools."*

According to Blue's positioning, the violence exerted by a supposedly anti-Spanish faction constitutes the main problem. This form of thematizing the conflict assumes a connection between not feeling Spanish and resorting to violence; a view that delegitimizes those who feel Basque instead of Spanish. This view suggests that while the "anti-Spanish" group lacks rights, the Spanish state has both the right and the duty to clamp down on those who use violence, and the idea of dialogue with them is dismissed. An additionally important aspect of Blue's view is the fact that she does not even mention the name of the region in question, i.e., the Basque Country. This distant, if not unfriendly, attitude towards this region can be perceived through her use of the third person plural when she refers to "the anti-Spanish feeling instilled into pupils in their schools", expressing an "Us vs. Them" interpretation of the conflict.

Her version of the peacemaking process is as follows:

"Thanks to a series of secret agreements between ETA and the Socialist Party, with many concessions made by the latter, a truce was achieved. During the supposed truce period, the Government was completely willing to hold talks with the terrorists while they kept on committing terrorist acts. Thousands of Spaniards marched, demanding that Zapatero stop yielding to ETA's claims. In turn, the People's Party split with the Government due to Zapatero's erroneous strategy. This event ended with the terrorist attack on Madrid Airport, which caused two casualties (this is, in fact, the only way ETA understands dialogue). After this attack, we are still supposed to believe that the Government has dropped negotiations with ETA."

In examining Blue's version of the events, we observe that, unlike in Green and Red's versions, she assesses the truce in quite a negative light, even going so far as to describe it as a "plot", termed as a conspiracy theory in the previous account, between the Socialist Government and ETA. Thus, from this perspective the position taken by the People's Party throughout the peace process is no longer regarded as failure to do its duty, but rather as a patriotic duty against an immoral agreement. Additionally, Blue is the only subject to explicitly mention the terrorist attack and the two resulting casualties. Interestingly, her comment on this event, which she referred to as ETA's only way of understanding dialogue, echoes Green's version in which the attack was a mere warning. Lastly, it is worth stressing that, according to this perspective, the very failure of the peacemaking process proves that dialogue is pointless, which reinforces the positioning of the People's Party against the government's attempt to reach a peace agreement with ETA.

Participant 4: Reddish – The fourth subject, "Reddish", is a 21-year-old female who studies psychology at the University of the Basque Country. Like participant 2 (Red), she also sympathizes with the Socialist Party, but unlike the former, she does not completely identify with the positioning of this party and its version of the truce period. Reddish's view on both the conflict and a possible resolution is as follows:

Thematization of the Basque conflict: *"Some radical sectors believe that the Basque Country should be independent from the Spanish state. Consequently, the terrorist organization ETA is trying to destabilize the political system by means of attacks. On the other hand, the political parties have been unable to find a peaceful solution to the conflict either."*

Conflict resolution: *“Dialogue is an essential ingredient in solving the conflict. Transparency and citizen information are also fundamental.”*

As we can see here, this participant, similarly to Blue, attributes the conflict to the alleged relationship between “some radical sectors” which would like the Basque Country to be independent and the existence of the terrorist group ETA. However, she also points out, as Red did, that the politicians are unable to find a peaceful solution using dialogue. From that standpoint, we can infer a positioning echoing Red’s in which politicians not only have the right, but also the duty, to seek dialogue. However, in this case the pursuit of dialogue goes hand in hand with the politicians’ duty to provide citizens with information on what is being negotiated. We can see that a new and previously absent collective actor has appeared on the stage, namely, the citizenry, an actor with the right to demand transparency and political accountability.

Her version of the truce period is as follows:

“On the 22nd of March, ETA announces a ceasefire which leads to a negotiation process. I don’t remember if this process started in secret or not. If so, it would be a deplorable beginning since I reckon it is our right to be informed about the Government’s terrorist policy. From the very outset, the Prime Minister Zapatero sought the cooperation of the People’s Party. However, the refusal of the latter, together with some innuendos launched against the Government, did not contribute to getting the process underway. Throughout the truce period Zapatero repeatedly stated his commitment to peace and dialogue, though in my opinion he did not treat us as fully responsible citizens, since he did not tell us the whole truth about the process. Yet, in spite of that, I supported and still support his attempt to achieve peace. However, amid

all that secrecy it was difficult to maintain faith in the truce, particularly when the Government was constantly evading decisive questions about its actions. Therefore, although the Opposition's discourse, accusing the Government of surrendering to ETA, was pure demagoguery, a lot of people (including myself) agreed with the People's Party's criticism of a number of obscure points regarding the process, e.g. a possible prior agreement with ETA. It is a well-known fact that, after having shown little sign of giving up violence (extorting money from Basque entrepreneurs and stockpiling weapons), ETA ended up planting a bomb at Barajas airport. This marked the end of a somewhat obscure and yet necessary peace process."

As can be seen here, the most complex and personal form of positioning regarding the Basque conflict is reflected in how the truce period has been reconstructed. On the one hand, we can see how Reddish partially adopts the Government's positioning, defending its right to achieve peace via dialogue and criticizing the obstructive stance of the People's Party throughout the process, as well as the accusations that it levies against the Government of giving in to ETA. On the other hand, however, we can see how this subject makes some of the People's Party's criticism of the apparent secretism of the Socialist Government during the negotiations her own. The result is a version of the truce period in which different voices and positionings are brought head to head, something that is clearly visible in the very structure of the narrative which, far from being linear, takes the form of a dialogue through the continued presence of conjunctions such as "although", "yet" or "however" throughout the account. Thus, without fully siding with the positionings of the actors in the conflict, Reddish uses some of their criticisms and claims to construct her own version of the peace process, with that version clearly containing a more personal positioning, identified by the idea

of a responsible citizenry with the right to be informed. That positioning (stemming from a comparison of the positioning of different actors in the conflict, particularly of the Socialist Government and the People's Party) is reflected in the more ambiguous, but at the same time, more open and complex, manner of defining the peace process at the end of the account as "an obscure and yet necessary process".

Discussion: Comparing the Cases

Throughout these four samples we have seen how the way in which participants thematize the Basque conflict has resulted in different versions of the truce period. Table 1 shows the subjects' thematization of the conflict together with their respective positionings. On observing this table we can note that thematizing an issue necessarily involves the assumption of a certain positioning in relation to it. If we consider the participants' account of the truce period in light of this table, it can be noted that each participant has remembered this episode in such a way that certain actions become justified or delegitimized according to a particular attribution of rights and duties. In this respect, it is worth noting the mediational role of narratives vis-à-vis the reconstruction of the truce period and the way in which justifications and accusations have been made throughout the discourse. As Bruner (1990) points out in respect of the role of narratives in recounting some polemical episode, they "become an instrument for telling not only what happened but also why it justified the action recounted" (p.86). Echoing John Austin's book *A plea for Excuses*, Bruner goes on to say that "a justification rests on a story of mitigating circumstances" (p.86), circumstances that would entitle certain actors to act in the way they did. However, actions carried out in the past are not only justified by means of discourse; the versions under analysis here suggest that some actions would appear to be interpreted as duties that have forced

certain actors to act in the way that they did. In that sense, the different ways of recounting the truce period have resulted in certain storylines “in which it becomes not only acceptable, but even one’s duty to undertake the actions in question” (Slocum, 2008, p. 209).

TABLE 1 HERE

In considering the way these subjects narrate the truce period, we observe that, in the case of Green’s account, ETA’s terrorist actions become justified in light of the oppressing circumstances allegedly surrounding the Basque people. Assuming ETA’s positioning, Green thematizes the conflict in such a way that the armed struggle (including the bomb attack at Madrid airport) can be considered as a community’s right (perhaps a duty) to defend itself against the alleged democratic deficit in the Spanish state. Green seems to buy into ETA’s version of the truce by conceiving it as a “democratic process” eventually ruined by the refusal of the Spanish state to allow the Basque Country to decide freely on its future. Conversely, in Red’s account the bomb attack is incompatible with what is considered a “peace process”, a process every responsible Government has the right (perhaps the duty) to explore. In view of that, the failure of the Socialist Government to achieve peace becomes mitigated by both ETA’s bomb attack and, to a lesser extent, the disloyal attitude of the People’s Party throughout the process. However, it is precisely the latter’s attitude which is justified in Blue’s account. Consistent with the People’s Party’s positioning on this matter, Blue depicts the opposition to Zapatero’s peace initiative as a legitimate and duty-bound response to what is considered a “truce-trap”. As for Reddish’s account, we have seen how, from her more personal way of positioning herself as a citizen with the right to demand political accountability, she justifies the Government’s peace initiative but also

legitimizes some criticism by the People's Party regarding the secrecy surrounding the negotiations.

As we can see, the first three participants, Green, Red and Blue, identify themselves with the positioning of certain political actors (ETA, the Socialist Government and the People's Party, respectively), thus assuming and to some extent reproducing their corresponding versions of the truce period, including the claims, criticisms and justifications contained in such versions. The result is three monological accounts in which each participant seems to adopt the voice of one of those actors, which is tantamount to saying that the actors' voices speak through the participants' accounts. From a Bakhtinian perspective, we could say that the participants have been to some degree talked—or ventriloquized—by those actors' voices, the dominance of which has “move[d] the self to the monological end of the continuum between dialogue and monologue” (Hermans & Dimaggio, 2007, p. 30). Yet, if we regard the three versions as a whole, we can see an example of what Wertsch (2002) calls hidden dialogism, inasmuch as each version constitutes an implicit response to a competing interpretation of the same episode⁷. This broader perspective highlights the importance of considering the argumentative context in which different voices and positionings compete to impose their own version of the conflict. As Billig (1987) points out, “one should consider the positions which are being criticized, or against which a justification is being mounted. Without knowing these counter-positions, the argumentative meaning will be lost” (p.121).

⁷ As Bakhtin (1986) states, “however monological the utterance may be [...], it cannot but be, in some measure, a response to what has already been said about the given topic” (p. 92).

However, the multivoiced dimension of the conflict not only becomes apparent through the dialogical relationship between different monological accounts dominated by certain voices; it also manifests itself through the internal dialogicality within those accounts in which a dialogue between voices linked to different positions is established. In this respect, we have seen how Reddish has brought the multivoicedness of the Basque conflict into her version of the truce period, thus converting heterodialogue between different voices in society into autodialogue within the self. As has been shown, this subject has used and compared the voices of different actors in the conflict in order to underpin her own positioning on it. This implies a higher degree of agency which takes shape in the way Reddish appropriates the words of others and reframes them through her own discourse, thus generating a more complex and personal account. Whereas in the previous cases the participants' words expressed the view of the main political actors on the truce period, in Red's case the words of those political actors are used to express the participant's own view of it.

Conclusions

As stated at the beginning of this paper, remembering cannot be conceived as an independent faculty that operates in a social vacuum in search of an accurate reproduction of the past. Through these case studies we have shown that remembering is affected by the different storylines provided by a particular socio-cultural setting. As shown here, the way in which subjects identify with the different political actors in the Basque conflict has influenced how they have interpreted the conflict, thus giving rise to different versions of the truce period, ranging from monological accounts (in which subjects assume and reproduce the voice of a single political actor, together with their

justifications and claims) to more dialogical and multivoiced versions (where participants appropriate some actors' voices in order to rebut them).

Such continuum between monologue and dialogue can provide some clues as to the future of conflicts by showing the extent to which individuals are rigidly stuck in certain positions or are more willing to accept dialogue and new forms of looking at the issue. As seen, assuming a monological perspective implies perpetuating the positioning of one party. This in turn entails adopting a particular storyline not only in order to reconstruct the past (by justifying actions that have been undertaken), but also to give sense to the present and the future (by legitimizing and encouraging different lines of action on the basis of a certain attribution of rights and duties). Taking the Schank and Abelson model (1977), we could say that individuals assume a script which provides some directionality by linking the past, the present and the future, a script that could take the following form: "we know this story, and we know its awful outcome, and we also know what must be done in response to it" (Tölölyan, 1989, p. 112). Conversely, moving to the dialogical end of that continuum would lead individuals to adopt a stance that, while potentially leading to increased ambiguity and uncertainty, can also offer new ways of transcending so-called mnemonic standoffs (Wertsch, in press). As Hermans and Dimaggio (2007) observe, "the dominance of one voice or a few voices over the others leads to a reduction of the experience of uncertainty, but at the same time, it has the questionable effect that other voices, as possible contributors or innovators of the self, are silenced or split off." (p. 39).

These questions lead us to consider the role of history teaching in relation to conflicts, particularly its potential role in tipping the balance in favour of one of the two ends of

the continuum between monologue and dialogue. On the one hand, history teaching has traditionally been used to transmit a monological account of the past by silencing other possible voices, thus fostering the “monologization of the dialogical self—a goal that is remarkably present for any social institution that attempts to capture the loyalties of the person” (Valsiner, 2002, p. 260). As Blanco and Rosa (1997) point out, this use of history is aimed at “reveal[ing] the scene in which one has to perform a role within an on-going drama” (p.3), thus rendering the individual a kind of actor vis-à-vis a ready-made script. On the other hand, however, history teaching can become a resource for promoting a more reflective way of dealing with the past. To that end, history teaching should reflect the increasing heterogeneity of today’s world, thus forcing individuals to deal with the ambiguity and multivoicedness surrounding historical accounts. This would imply bringing the complexity of society to the self in order to encourage individuals to critically use, and respond to, the wide range of existing voices on a particular issue, thereby enabling them to co-construct their own personal positioning in its regard. The whole point would be to endow individuals with more agency so that they can change from being *actors*, subjected to ready-made scripts, to becoming *authors* capable of imagining new and more personal ways of looking at old conflicts.

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Table 1

Thematization of the Basque Conflict and Participants' Positionings

	<i>Thematization of the conflict</i>	<i>Participants' positionings</i>
Green	Oppression and lack of freedom to decide the Basque Country's own future.	Right (and duty?) to decide the Basque Country's own future and to fight for this right.
Red	Conflict of interests (with an identity base) where arms prevail over words.	Right (and duty?) to find a way out of the conflict through dialogue.
Blue	Problem of violence caused by anti-Spanish sentiments.	Right (and duty?) to impede any concession to terrorist groups and to reinforce policing action.
Reddish	Problem of violence caused by radical groups and inability of politicians to reach a peaceful solution.	Right (and duty?) to find a way out of the conflict through dialogue. Duty to inform the citizenry on the state of negotiations.